

EMPIRICAL BASIS OF FORMATION OF VOCATIONAL QUALITIES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the concept of will and the essence of will qualities, their specific characteristics, and the processes of formation of will qualities in students, as well as their effect on work, appreciation of work, self-management, their pedagogical and psychological processes, and scientific theories of the concept of will extensive information is provided.*

Keywords: *Will, volitional characteristics, will of young people, steadfastness, determination, confidence, lack of will, education, training, the importance of the educational process, will disorders, self-control, courage, determination, endurance, tolerance, principle, strength, character, virtue, level, duality, character.*

INTRODUCTION. In psychological literature, methodology is defined as the teaching of methods. It is emphasized that its content includes a set of management principles, methods, and methods of cognitive activity. In this way, achieving the goal, effective guidance, objective knowledge fund is ensured. Proportionality of achieving the goal set before the person with voluntary behavior is the essence or importance of the method is to reflect the "way to achieve the goal". In psychology, there are cases of understanding them as a description of the operational aspect of behavior. Now the attitude of psychologists and philosophers to the concepts of "method" and "definition" will be analyzed.

A broad understanding of the method can also be found in the encyclopedia of philosophy. In it, it is said that "it is a form of theoretical and practical acquisition of existence, arising from the laws of the movement of the studied object." For example, "the method prevails in a consistent unity with the theory, in gradualism: any objective knowledge system can be a method. Strictly speaking, method is theory satisfied by practice or practice-oriented research itself. "Any law of science appears as a principle to be understood in the future, as a method of knowledge"

M.V. Mostepanenko tried to give a popular expression of the above understanding of method and methodology: "The way of knowing, based on a specific set of previously acquired general knowledge, is a method. Methodology is a teaching about the principles and methods of knowledge" [119]. Due to the fact that the method is related to preliminary knowledge, the methodology is divided into two parts: a) teaching about the principles and primary foundations of knowledge;

b) teaching about methods and techniques based on those principles [119]. Evaluation and analysis of perceptions and views by the researcher in the process of cognition is the first part of cognition. This part of the methodology is directly related to philosophy, worldview. The general aspects of the special methods of knowledge that make up its general methodology are interpreted in the teaching on research methods. In this definition, the limitation of understanding as a set of technical means, methods of organizing research, or the basis of knowledge, both philosophical and worldview, is excluded.

The second type of scientific view is characteristic of positivist scientists and denies the role of worldview in knowledge. Understanding the term methodology in a narrow sense, seeing

it as a synonym of methodology is also found in the works of former Soviet researchers. V.A. Yadov does not include any of the three stages that he distinguished from the methodological analysis. As a result, the methodological status of the organization of the research, the implementation aspect, and the methodological side are deprived of reflection [178]. For the same reason, it is desirable to understand the essence and importance of methodological analysis, to distinguish the characteristics of researchers' use of terms. Many researchers understand the concept of "method" more narrowly, as a result, they are not limited to defining methodology as a teaching about the method of scientific knowledge. According to E.G. Yudin's definition of methodology, it is a teaching about means, methods, logical organization, structure of activity [177].

Although the term "methodology" in our research is close to the above interpretations, it has some differences both in form and content. The study subject of the methodology of psychology includes information on the subject, criteria, categories, principles, laws, mechanisms, properties, qualities, stages, phases of development, approaches of the science. In our opinion, when thinking about methodology, there can certainly be a special form of reflection, sharing information about self-awareness. In psychology, self-awareness is a special form of information system that has a complex nature of scientific knowledge. At this point, it is important to reflect on the ways of determining the internal and external determinants of cognitive processes, to provide information on its structure, critical evaluation of acquired knowledge, and description of its connection with practice.

Due to the fact that experimental psychology is separate as a field, this factor is included in the subject of research. The successful completion of a person's activities, behavior and behavior largely depends on a person's emotional states, experiences and high feelings. If the successful course of activities, the manifestation of behavior in interpersonal relations is evaluated as a positive psychological state, it is recognized that emotions and feelings prevail in a stable direction towards the goal. The presence of qualities of strength, stability, perfection of feelings means that they have become dynamic stereotypes. A person's interaction with nature and society - causes periodic and temporary changes in the norms of dealing with them.

The implementation of human activity and behavior based on certain laws depends on both objective and subjective conditions. It consists of objective conditions, that is, micro and macro, that is, material existence, the availability of auxiliary means, the ability to meet their requirements, the interference of external stimuli, the compatibility of time and space dimensions. The presence of a system of natural conditions for the manifestation of behavior and activity serves as factors that ensure their success. In addition to failure in natural conditions, the occurrence of certain deficiencies and interruptions causes defects.

Under the influence of natural conditions and the environment, a number of qualitative and quantitative changes occur in the human psyche. They are manifested in updates, in the birth of new qualities and characteristics. The geographical environment, which is a component of the natural environment, plays an important role in this regard. First of all, it affects the biologically determined qualities of a person and turns phenotypes into genotypes. Secondly, during ontogenesis, it affects the natural formation of characterological features of a person. As a result, it acts as a mechanism that ensures harmony between the microenvironment and genes, hereditary characters. In addition to the objective conditions, the subjective conditions, which are inextricably linked with the human factor, ensure the effective implementation of behavior, activity, and

behavior in social life. Subjective conditions include stability of personality, strength of character, need, motive, skill, thoroughness of potential, the formation of self-management, the harmony of biologically determined traits.

Due to changes in objective and subjective conditions, the priority of positive or negative psychological states, events, traits, and experiences occurs. This reduces the activity of the higher nervous system, the rhythm of the central nervous system (CNS), and the ability to work. As a result of this, the usual efforts, operations, rituals in the implementation of activity, behavior, behavior begin to be disturbed. Extreme nervousness, mental defect, deviance from law, rule of unpleasant experiences lead. The success of activity, behavior and behavior will be questioned. The dominance of self-productivity, stability, and goal-orientation qualities will disappear. As a result, unfulfilled good intentions and high emotions continue to reign as dreams.

In our opinion, it is also possible to solve some problems in a simple way:

- 1) a person is a conscious being, regardless of whether he has the power of creativity, he is subject to the influence of nature, instincts, unconditional reflexes;
- 2) the person's organism is not adapted to emergency events and situations;
- 3) due to the fact that the person has not reached the level of perfection, it is not possible to notice the consequences of causal connection, feelings of fear in advance, to have a counter-effect;
- 4) the lack of formation of a second image in a person can make him a victim of danger.

According to data analysis, no one is immune to failure, because social immunity has the potential to react very weakly. As long as perfection does not become the spiritual world of the subject, no one will accept accidents and emergency situations as normal events. According to theoretical considerations, smooth and efficient activity, behavior and behavior depend genetically on the following:

- a) existence of objective and subjective conditions;
- b) to the impact of random emergency situations that change the prevailing objective and subjective conditions;
- c) emotions and feelings acquire positive and negative characteristics;
- g) the stability of personality and characterological characteristics of a person;
- d) that a person has reached the level of perfection, etc.

In order to achieve success in life and work, and to direct efforts towards it, it is permissible to pay attention to the following:

- 1) to make corrections to objective and subjective conditions if they change;
- 2) influence a person to get used to emergency situations with the help of training;
- 3) to increase the body's resistance to the elements;
- 4) to improve the sense of striving for perfection;
- 5) to help the individual realize his potential, etc.

There are leading factors that change a person's life and activities, and they are subject to the influence of the individual to a certain extent.

It should be noted that there are many methods in the psychological literature aimed at determining the problem of the orientation of a person, levels of commitment in certain areas. We know from these works "Level of development of reflexivity" (A.V. Karpov), "Study of voluntary qualities of a person" (V.M. Shumakov), "Style of self-management of behavior" (V.I.

Morosanova) and "Voluntary self-management methodology" (A.V. Zverkov and Y.V. Eidman) were used.

Conclusion. Therefore, through the application of this methodology, it is to find psychological solutions of an individual approach to each person based on indicators of the degree of formation of voluntary qualities in students.

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